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Manuscripts should be submitted thorough the dedicated email (psychology@unilorin.edu.ng) using Microsoft word, Times New Roman Font size 12 with double line spacing. The APA (7th Edition) references style should be adopted and article with reference should not exceed 6000 words.

The Editor-in-Chief

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**Health Seeking Behaviour and Health Locus of Control as Predictors of Cyberchondria
among the Elderly Residents in Ekiti State**

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Abstract

This study examines the relationships among cyberchondria severity, HLC, and health-seeking behaviour (differentiated into online, professional, and traditional searches) among elderly individuals in Ado Ekiti, Nigeria. A cross-sectional survey was administered to one hundred and fifty elderly participants. Standardized instruments were used: the Cyberchondria Severity Scale, Health Locus of Control Scale and a Health-Seeking Behaviour Questionnaire. The study found that cyberchondria severity was strongly and positively correlated with online health search behaviour and moderately correlated with overall. In the regression model, professional health search and health locus of control emerged as significant predictors of cyberchondria severity. The findings indicate that excessive online health information seeking is associated with increased cyberchondria among older adults, especially for those with a more external HLC. These results underscore the need for interventions that enhance digital health literacy and foster a stronger internal locus of control to alleviate health related anxiety in this vulnerable population. Future research should employ longitudinal designs to further elucidate the causal pathways among these variables.

Keywords: Cyberchondria, Anxiety, Health locus of control, Elderly, Health seeking behavior.

Introduction

Traditionally, health information was primarily sought from healthcare professionals, books, and, in many cultures, from family elders or community healers. This reliance on face-to-face consultations provided a sense of authority and trust, as well as the opportunity for personalized advice and reassurance. However, with the advent of the internet in the late 20th century, a dramatic shift occurred, making health information more accessible and diversifying health knowledge on a global scale (Starcevic & Berle, 2013). The internet has not only enabled rapid access to information but has also increased the volume and variety of health-related resources available to the public. As a result, individuals can now investigate health concerns independently, sometimes bypassing traditional health providers. This self-directed approach has potential benefits, such as empowering individuals to take an active role in their health management, but it also presents notable risks, particularly the spread of misinformation and the exacerbation of health anxiety, commonly referred to as "cyberchondria" (White & Horvitz (2009).

Cyberchondria describes the phenomenon of excessive health-related internet searching, often driven by anxiety and leading to further distress instead of reassurance. This can result in a cycle of persistent worry, self-diagnosis, and ultimately increased anxiety, which is particularly concerning among vulnerable populations (Fergus & Spada, 2017). With Nigeria's internet penetration increasing significantly over the past decade, more Nigerians, including older adults, now have access to online health information (Nigerian Communications Commission, 2021) However, for older adults, this increased access is often accompanied by unique vulnerabilities. The aged population, generally defined as individuals aged 50 and above, may have lower digital literacy levels, making it challenging to navigate and critically assess online health information. Additionally, factors such as cognitive decline and social isolation can make older adults more susceptible to the anxiety inducing effects of cyberchondria (Ige & Nwachukwu, 2020).

In Ado Ekiti, Ekiti State, where healthcare access is limited and traditional healthcare systems are often strained, many elderly individuals turn to the internet as an alternative source of health information. Although this can be beneficial, it can also result in overreliance on potentially inaccurate or alarming information, contributing to unnecessary anxiety and the cycle of cyberchondria (Ige & Nwachukwu, 2020). Older adults face specific challenges in the digital

landscape, which can intensify the effects of cyberchondria. Digital literacy remains a significant barrier, as many elderly individuals have limited experience navigating the complexities of the internet. Studies have shown that lower levels of digital literacy are correlated with difficulty discerning reliable sources, leading to increased susceptibility to misinformation and anxiety (Lauckner & Hsieh, 2013).

We also have cognitive aging effects like mild memory loss, which can augment health anxiety in the case of old people accessing health information on the internet. This experience can be further enhanced by social isolation that is prevalent in older adults since this lack of immediate social support or professional reassurance can result in repetitive and excessive searches online on health as a coping mechanism (McMullan, Berle, Arnáez, and Starcevic, 2019). Though there are past studies that have been able to establish several psychosocial factors associated with cyberchondria, little focus has been drawn on how the individual belief systems affect the development of this behaviour in the elderly. Specifically, health locus of control could affect the perceptions, interpretation, and action of older adults concerning the received health information on the Internet. Those who feel that their health is mainly dependent on external factors might tend to indulge in excessive searching on the internet, thus making them develop more anxiety. Regardless of the topicality of this construct, there is little empirical research studies that investigate the value of health locus of control as a predictor of cyberchondria among the older population, particularly in the Nigerian context. This is one of the gaps that necessitate the exploration of health locus of control and health-seeking behaviour in the prediction of cyberchondria among elderly people living in Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State.

In Nigeria, health-seeking behaviour is strongly influenced by cultural and societal factors, including traditional medicine, family dynamics, and community values. Traditional medicine remains a widely respected approach to health management, with many elderly individuals incorporating both traditional practices and modern healthcare methods. Family and community play a crucial role, often acting as intermediaries in health decisions and influencing attitudes toward health information sources (Ogunsola, Adebayo & Ojo, 2021).

However, the increasing use of digital resources for health information introduces a shift in this paradigm, particularly among the aged. This shift is not without challenges, as older adults in Nigeria may find themselves navigating the unfamiliar territory of online health information with little guidance. The combination of cultural reliance on family and traditional medicine, along with limited digital literacy, can contribute to an increased likelihood of cyberchondria,

as elderly individuals may struggle to reconcile traditional health beliefs with the sometimes-alarming information found online (Ige & Nwachukwu, 2020). Understanding these cultural and societal dynamics is essential to contextualizing cyberchondria among Nigeria's elderly. The study aims at empirically identifying the connection between health-seeking behaviour, health locus of control and cyberchondria among the older people in Ado-Ekiti. Despite the past studies addressing health-seeking behavior and health locus of control as two distinct factors in relation to health outcomes, the potential empirical support of the variables directly correlating with cyberchondria especially in older adults is very little. Such shortcomings of empirical interrelationship require a systematic study on the prediction of cyberchondria by these independent variables on the elderly population. As a result, the given study has a reasonable rationale to develop and test research hypotheses, as well as evidence-based arguments that can be utilized by health providers and policymakers to facilitate the adoption of more healthy online health information-seeking behavior among older adults living in Ado-Ekiti.

Methods

Research Design

This study employed a cross-sectional, correlational research design to investigate the relationships between health-seeking behavior, health locus of control, and cyberchondria among older adults in Ado Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria. A cross-sectional approach allowed for the examination of these variables at a single point in time, while the correlational design enabled the exploration of associations and predictive relationships without manipulation. This design was suitable for capturing the dynamics of these variables in the target population.

Participants

The participants in this study were older adults aged 50 years and above residing in Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State. In addition to age, relevant demographic characteristics such as gender, marital status, educational level, employment or retirement status, and access to digital devices were considered in describing the study population. These characteristics were included because they may influence health-seeking behaviour, exposure to online health information, and the ability to interpret digital health content. The population was selected due to its increased likelihood of experiencing age-related health concerns, engaging in health-seeking behaviours, and facing challenges related to digital literacy and health-related anxiety.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

A total of 200 participants were selected using a hybrid sampling approach that combined convenience and purposive sampling. Convenience sampling was applied by selecting participants from accessible community locations, such as health centers, churches, and social gatherings. Purposive sampling ensured that participants met the study's inclusion criteria, aligning with its focus on older adults who engaged in online health-seeking behaviors. The use of multiple selection sites helped reduce biases and ensured a diverse sample in terms of gender, education, and socioeconomic background. The success rate of compliance among the respondents is attributed to the nature of the research and the age of the respondents, the respondents were educated on the relevance and benefits of the research, hence their cooperation.

Measures

Three validated instruments were used to measure the primary variables of cyberchondria, health-seeking behaviour, and health locus of control. Each instrument was selected for its strong psychometric properties and relevance to the constructs being assessed.

Cyberchondria Severity Scale – 12 Item Version (CSS-12)

The Cyberchondria Severity Scale – 12 Item Version (CSS-12) is a shortened version of the original CSS, validated by McElroy and Shevlin (2014) to measure the severity of cyberchondria symptoms efficiently. The CSS-12 evaluates the following dimensions:
Compulsion: The extent to which participants felt compelled to search for health information online.

Distress: Emotional discomfort or anxiety caused by online health information.

Excessiveness: The frequency and intensity of online health-related searches.

Reassurance-Seeking: Dependence on online health information for reassurance.

Mistrust of Medical Professionals: The impact of online information on trust in healthcare providers.

The CSS-12 consists of 12 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("Strongly Disagree") to 5 ("Strongly Agree"). It has demonstrated excellent internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha values exceeding 0.85, and strong construct validity through its correlations with health anxiety and general anxiety measures. Its brevity and robust psychometric properties made it particularly suitable for this study, ensuring ease of use among older adults.

Health Locus of Control Scale (HLCS)

The Health Locus of Control Scale (HLCS), developed by Wallston, Wallston, and DeVellis (1978) is a well-established tool for assessing beliefs about control over health outcomes. The HLCS consists of three subscales:

Internal Locus of Control: The belief that personal actions determine health outcomes.

Powerful Others (External): The belief that health outcomes depend on medical professionals or other authoritative figures.

Chance (External): The belief that health outcomes are governed by luck or fate.

The scale consisted of 18 items rated on a 6-point Likert scale from 1 ("Strongly Disagree") to 6 ("Strongly Agree"). Higher scores on the external subscales indicated greater reliance on external control, while higher scores on the internal subscale reflected stronger personal health control beliefs. The HLCS has demonstrated reliability (Cronbach's alpha: 0.70–0.85) and validity in distinguishing between internal and external health orientations.

Health-Seeking Behavior Questionnaire (HSBQ)

The Health-Seeking Behavior Questionnaire (HSBQ), adapted from Barke, Nyenhuis, and Kröner-Herwig (2020), measured the frequency, motivations, and nature of participants' online health-seeking behaviors. Key dimensions assessed included:

Frequency of Searches: How often participants searched for health-related information online.

Content of Searches: The specific health topics explored, such as symptoms, treatments, or preventive measures.

Motivations for Searching: Reasons for seeking health information, including curiosity, self-diagnosis, or preparation for medical consultations.

Outcomes of Searches: Participants' experiences with the information, such as whether it provided reassurance, caused confusion, or heightened anxiety.

The HSBQ demonstrated strong reliability in prior studies, with a Cronbach's alpha above 0.80, and its construct validity was confirmed through correlations with self-reported health behaviors and outcomes.

Procedure for Data Collection

Data collection was conducted over a 4–6-week period by the researchers. Questionnaires were distributed to participants at community locations, including health centers, churches, and social gatherings. Participants received clear instructions for completing the questionnaires

independently, and the researcher arranged follow-ups for collecting completed forms to ensure data accuracy and completeness.

The researchers shared printed copies of the questionnaires with selected participants at identified locations. Written consent was obtained before participants received the questionnaires. Participants were informed of the study’s purpose, confidentiality measures, and their rights to withdraw at any time. Participants were allowed to complete the questionnaires at their convenience. The researchers coordinated the retrieval of completed forms through scheduled visits or drop-off arrangements.

Methods of Data Analysis

The data was analysed using IBM-SPSS Version 25. Regression, Pearson and Spearman’s Rho method was used to test hypotheses.

Results

Table 1: Pearson Correlation Matrix

Variables	Cyberchondria Severity	Online Health Search	Professional Health Search	Traditional Health Search	Health Locus of Control
Cyberchondria Severity	1	.557	.270	.095	.293
Online Health Search	.557	1	.165	.008	.244
Professional Health Search	.270	.165	1	.200	.161
Traditional Health Search	.095	.008	.200	1	.004
Health Locus of Control	.293	.244	.161	.004	1

To test the relationships among the severity of cyberchondria, health-seeking behaviours, and health locus of control, Pearson product -moment correlation analysis was performed. These results revealed that there was a positive strong relationship between cyberchondria severity and online health search, $r = 0.56$, $p = -0.01$, which indicated that the severity of cyberchondria was correlated with higher cyberchondria levels among the aged because of the online search of information about their health. The severity of cyberchondria was also positively but moderately related to health locus

of control, $r = .29$, $p < .01$, and indicated that people who viewed their health outcomes as a factor of external influence in the future were more prone to cyberchondria. Moreover, online health search was weak and significantly associated with professional health search, $r = .17$, $p < .05$, which suggests online acquisition of information can lead to a decision to visit a medical practitioner. Professional health search also was found to have a weak positive correlation with traditional health search, $r = .20$, $p < .05$, suggesting that a minor group of users blend professional and traditional healthcare.

Table 2: Spearman’s Rho Correlation Matrix

Variables	Cyberchondria Severity	Online Health Search	Professional Health Search	Traditional Health Search	Health Locus of Control
Cyberchondria Severity	1	.557	.270	.095	.293
Online Health Search	.557	1	.165	.008	.244
Professional Health Search	.270	.165	1	.200	.161
Traditional Health Search	.095	.008	.200	1	.004
Health Locus of Control	.293	.244	.161	.004	1

To further test the relationships of the study variables, Spearman rho correlation analysis was done to evaluate the monotonic relationships between the variables. The results of the analysis showed that there was a moderate positive correlation between cyberchondria severity and the online health search, $\rho = .51$, $p < .01$, which means that the more the elderly participated in the online health information seeking, the higher the severity of cyberchondria. There was also a weak yet significant positive correlation between the severity of cyberchondria and health locus of control, $\rho = .23$, $p < .01$, indicating that a slight positive relationship existed between those who felt that their health was affected by external factors and cyberchondria. Also, online health search had a low correlation with professional health search, $\rho = .16$, $p < .05$, which means that the use of online information seeking can occasionally be prior or can trigger the use of healthcare professionals. Professional health search and traditional health search were also

found to show a weak positive relationship, $\rho = .20$, $p < .05$ which means that there are people who prefer a combination of professional medical care with traditional health practices.

Table 3: Model Summary of multiple regression analysis to examine the predictive role of health-seeking behavior (professional health search, search for traditional health) and health locus of control on cyberchondria severity

Predictor Variables	B	Std. Error	β	t	Sig.
Constant	.358	.629	—	.569	.570
Professional Health Search	.502	.182	.219	2.753	.007
Traditional Health Search	.140	.219	.050	.638	.524
Health Locus of Control	.399	.121	.257	3.303	.001

Notes: B = Unstandardized coefficient; β = Standardized coefficient; Sig. = Significance level; Dependent Variable: Cyberchondria Severity

Multiple regression was done to test the degree to which the health-seeking behaviour and health locus of control had the roles of predicting the severity of cyberchondria among the elderly residents of Ado Ekiti. The findings showed that professional health search was a strong predictor of the severity of cyberchondria, $B = 0.50$, $SE = 0.18$, $\beta = 0.22$, $t = 2.75$, $p = .007$. This result implies that the more people seek professional health information, the more cyberchondria they have. Traditional health search did not significantly predict the severity of cyberchondria, $B = 0.14$, $SE = 0.22$, $\beta = 0.05$, $t = 0.64$, $p = .524$, which implies that the use of traditional health source of information is not a significant source of cyberchondria severity among the aged population in the study. Health locus of control was another important predictor of the severity of cyberchondria, $B = 0.40$, $SE = 0.12$, $\beta = 0.26$, $t = 3.30$, $p = .001$. The meaning of this outcome is that beliefs about health outcome control are greatly linked with the severity of cyberchondria. In short, the results indicate that professional health search and health locus of control are both significant predictors of the severity of cyberchondria among elderly residents in Ado Ekiti, but does not indicate a significant predictive value of search of traditional health.

Discussion

This paper has explored how health-seeking behaviour, health locus of control, and severity of cyberchondria are related to each other among the elderly people in Ado Ekiti. The results suggest the empirical evidence that online and professional health-seeking behaviours and health locus of control are important factors in developing cyberchondria in older adults.

In line with Hypothesis One, the findings showed that online health search and severity of cyberchondria are strongly related. This result is consistent with findings of other researchers (Starcevic and Berle, 2013; White and Horvitz, 2009) who also indicate that the anxiety about health may be heightened through recurrent exposure to unfiltered and often frightening online medical information. The older adults might be especially susceptible because of low digital literacy and the lack of ability to assess the reliability of online sources, which cause excessive reassurance-seeking and the further growth of concern. The identified positive correlation between professional health search and cyberchondria severity is also substantiated by the existing body of literature which allows assuming that the frequent visits to health professionals can be merely a symptom of the underlying health anxiety and not a successful reassurance (McElroy et al., 2019). Professional validation is often sought by individuals who have difficulties with the tolerance of uncertainty thus strengthening anxiety instead of eliminating it.

On the contrary, the severity of cyberchondria did not significantly relate with traditional health-seeking behaviour. Such a result can occur due to the familiar and culturally based traditional health practices, which can be less threatening and less information-based compared to online ones. In comparison to digital platforms which often depict the worst-case scenarios, traditional health information is usually distributed in trusted social networks and might not cause significant anxiety.

In line with Hypothesis Two, health locus of control was connected to severity of cyberchondria significantly. Older persons who had an external locus of control in their health were more prone to an elevated level of cyberchondria. This finding is in line with the locus of control theory by Rotter and previous researchers who opine that when faced with ambiguous health information, persons who hold beliefs in fate, chance, or external powers will be more likely

to get anxious (Wallston et al., 1978). The feeling of lack of control over a person can also lead to increased suffering when the information found on the web seems to be contradicting or frightening.

These relationships were further explained with the regression analysis which showed that severity of cyberchondria was predicted by professional health search and health locus of control independently. It is implied that cyberchondria in the elderly population is not only spurred by exposure of information, but also spurred by psychological orientation on health control. Nevertheless, traditional health search was not found to play an important role in cases where the other predictors were controlled, which supports the notion that digital and formal medical paths are more pivotal to the development of cyberchondria. All in all, these results highlight the complexity of cyberchondria in old age. The findings emphasise the significance of interventions that enhance moderate health information-seeking behaviours, enhance digital health literacy, and develop a greater internal health locus of control. This can be beneficial in alleviating anxiety and assisting older people to connect with health information more adaptively and in a manner that is more emotionally controlled.

Conclusion

This paper has explored the correlation between the severity of cyberchondria, health-seeking behaviour, and health locus of control of the elderly living in Ado Ekiti. The results revealed a significant correlation between the severity of cyberchondria and health information seeking patterns and beliefs of individuals in the control over health outcomes.

The outcomes showed that there is a positive significant correlation between online health search and cyberchondria severity, meaning that older people who regularly visit websites to find health information are more prone to experience the increased level of health-related anxiety. It was also found that professional health search had a significant relation to and prediction of the severity of cyberchondria with the evident assertion that recurring use of formal medical sources might reflect or enhance the anxiety and not reassure it. Conversely, traditional health-seeking behaviour did not exhibit a significant correlation with the severity of cyberchondria and did not predict cyberchondria when it was adjusted by other factors.

The locus of control of health was found to be a significant issue of severity of cyberchondria. The elderly who had more external orientation with regard to health control were greatly more probable to report greater levels of cyberchondria. This implies that the perceptions of health outcomes as a factor that is affected by external influence are correlated with greater susceptibility to anxiety as a result of health information seeking. On the whole, the results suggest that online and professional health-seeking behaviours plus health locus of control are very important factors that contribute to cyberchondria among elderly residents in Ado Ekiti, although, not much importance is given to traditional health-seeking practices. The findings present a case that emphasises the significance of using behavioural and psychological variables in the management of cyberchondria among the older age groups.

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